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A UNIFIED ARCHITECTURE FOR FAST HEVC INTRA-PREDICTION CODING

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Abstract:	<p>The High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) is the new video coding standard, which obtains over 50% bit rate savings compared with H.264/AVC for the same perceptual quality. Intra-prediction coding in HEVC achieves high coding performance in expense of high computational complexity, due to the exhaustive evaluation of all available Coding Units (CU) sizes, with up to 35 prediction modes for each CU, selecting the one with the lower rate distortion cost, among other new features. This paper presents a Unified Architecture to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision (FPMD). This approach combines a Fast Partitioning Decision (FPD) algorithm, based on decision trees, which are trained using Machine Learning (ML) techniques, and a Fast Mode Decision (FMD) algorithm, based on a novel texture orientation detection algorithm, which computes the mean directional variance along a set of co-lines with rational slopes using a sliding window over the Prediction Unit (PU). Both algorithms proposed apply a similar approach, exploiting the strong correlation between several image features and the optimal CTU partitioning and the optimal prediction mode. The key point of the combined approach is that both algorithms compute the image features with low complexity, and the partition decision and the mode decision can also be taken with low complexity, using decision trees (if-else statements) and by selecting the minimum directional variance between a reduced set of directions. This approach can be implemented using any combination of nodes, obtaining a wide range of time savings, from 44% to 67%, and light penalties from 1.1% to 4.6%. Comparisons with similar state-of-the-art works show the proposed approach achieves the best trade-off between complexity reduction and rate-distortion.</p>	

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ABSTRACT

The *High Efficiency Video Coding* (HEVC) is the new video coding standard, which obtains over 50% bit rate savings compared with H.264/AVC for the same perceptual quality. Intra-prediction coding in HEVC achieves high coding performance in expense of high computational complexity, due to the exhaustive evaluation of all available *Coding Units* (CU) sizes, with up to 35 prediction modes for each CU, selecting the one with the lower rate distortion cost, among other new features. This paper presents a *Unified Architecture* to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD). This approach combines a *Fast Partitioning Decision* (FPD) algorithm, based on decision trees, which are trained using *Machine Learning* (ML) techniques, and a *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD) algorithm, based on a novel texture orientation detection algorithm, which computes the mean directional variance along a set of *co-lines* with rational slopes using a sliding window over the *Prediction Unit* (PU). Both algorithms proposed apply a similar approach, exploiting the strong correlation between several image features and the optimal CTU partitioning and the optimal prediction mode. The key point of the combined approach is that both algorithms compute the image features with low complexity, and the partition decision and the mode decision can also be taken with low complexity, using decision trees (if-else statements) and by selecting the minimum directional variance between a reduced set of directions. This approach can be implemented using any combination of nodes, obtaining a wide range of time savings, from 44% to 67%, and light penalties from 1.1% to 4.6%. Comparisons with similar state-of-the-art works show the proposed approach achieves the best trade-off between complexity reduction and rate-distortion.

Key Words: *HEVC; Intra-Prediction; Machine Learning; Texture Orientation; Directional Variance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The new video coding standard, known as High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) [1], has been approved by the Joint Collaborative Team Video Coding (JCT-VC) working group, from ITU and ISO organizations. HEVC has already replaced the successful H.264/AVC standard [2], especially for high-resolution formats beyond HD, like the Ultra High Definition formats termed as 4K and 8K. The new HEVC video coding tools allow to achieve bit rate savings of over 50% compared to H.264/AVC, for the same objective video quality [3]. Furthermore, HEVC also outperforms other widespread video codecs used in the Internet such as VP8 and VP9 [4].

Special interest has aroused the high performance of HEVC using exclusively intra-picture tools for the still images coding, showing gains around 40% compared with the successful JPEG-2000 standard [5]. There are several particular scenarios in which intra-picture coding is the optimal choice, such as still-picture photography storage, live TV interviews where low latency is needed for natural communication between the interlocutors, and also for professional edition and post-production tasks commonly used in the TV and cinema industries, where high quality and fast access to the individual pictures are required. These production codecs, named *mezzanine* codecs, are highly relevant for the audio-visual industry, which demands two things: very high compression efficiency and a low computational burden. For this reason, the HEVC standard has approved a set of specific profiles that exclusively use the intra-prediction schema, known as the “*Main Still Picture*” and “*Main Intra*” profiles, with support for different bit depths and chroma sampling formats.

The high HEVC intra-coding performance is mainly attributable to two novel tools, the new flexible quad-tree picture partitioning [6], named Coding Tree Unit (CTU), and the new high density of angular predictors for the mode decision [7]. The pictures are divided in CTUs, which can be recursively split to form a quad-tree structure with three new unit types: Coding Unit (CU), Prediction Unit (PU) and Transform Unit (TU). The CUs, PUs and TUs cover a size range from 64x64 to 4x4, adapting the size of the coding

1 units to the local image complexity, taking use of largest sizes for homogeneous regions
2 and smaller sizes for complex textured areas. With the aim of achieving the best intra-
3 coding performance an exhaustive evaluation of the whole number of possible CU, PU,
4 and TU sizes and the full number of available prediction modes is carried out by using a
5 well-known Rate Distortion Optimization (RDO) technique [8]. While such flexibility
6 leads to high compression efficiency, it comes at the expenses of a huge computational
7 burden, primarily due to the large number of available directional predictors and PU sizes
8 [9], which is hindering the rapid adoption of HEVC by the professional market [10][11].
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Multiple approaches have been proposed in the literature for the reduction of the HEVC complexity, many of which focus on the reductions of the number of block sizes to be evaluated by using a tree pruning scheme. Other approaches are centered in the detection of the most probable intra direction, in order to avoid the evaluation of the full range of prediction modes by the RDO.

The speeding up of the intra-prediction coding can be achieved by applying advanced techniques that allow the taking of decisions that are needed in the different stages of intra-prediction with low complexity. This approach constitutes the basis of this paper, which addresses the complexity reduction of HEVC intra-coding by using non-traditional techniques used in the video coding standards, such as Machine Learning (ML) and image processing algorithms for texture orientation detection. This paper presents a *Unified Architecture* to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD). This approach combines, in a first stage, a *Fast Partitioning Decision* (FPD) algorithm, based on decision trees, which are trained using ML techniques, and in a second stage, a *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD) algorithm, based on a novel texture orientation detection algorithm, which computes the mean directional variance along a set of *co-lines* with rational slopes using a sliding window over the PU. Both algorithms apply a similar approach, exploiting the strong correlation between several image features and the optimal PU partitioning and the optimal prediction mode. The key point of the combined approach is that both algorithms compute the image features with

1 low complexity, and the partition decision and the mode decision can also be taken with
2 low complexity, using decision trees and by selecting the minimum directional variance
3
4 between a reduced set of directions.
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6 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. An overview of the HEVC intra-
7 prediction schema is introduced in Section II. Section III presents a review of the fast intra-
8 prediction approaches recently proposed in the literature. Section IV presents the details of
9 our *Fast Partitioning Decision* (FPD) algorithm and our *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD)
10 algorithm to form the *Unified Architecture* proposed for fast HEVC intra-prediction
11 coding, while the experimental results are shown in Section V. We summarize the
12 conclusions in Section VI.
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23 **II. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND**

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26 HEVC can be considered an evolution of the H.264/AVC, since it maintains the same
27 block-based ‘hybrid’ architecture used in previous video compression standards, by
28 applying inter-picture prediction for temporal decorrelation, and intra-picture prediction
29 for the spatial image decorrelation. In addition, new tools have been introduced in HEVC
30 that increase its coding efficiency compared to H.264/AVC, such as a new coding unit
31 partitioning scheme named Coding Tree Unit (CTU), a new angular intra-prediction
32 algorithm, new transform sizes of 16×16 and 32×32 , and a new filter in the decoding loop
33 termed Sample Adaptive Offset (SAO). A detailed description of those tools and a general
34 overview of the HEVC architecture can be found in [12].
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46 The CTUs in intra-prediction can be iteratively partitioned into four square sub-blocks
47 of half resolution, thus it can be considered as a hierarchical tree where each branch ends
48 in a node, which determines the CUs. Each CU is by itself a new root of two new trees that
49 contain the PUs and TUs. The maximum CTU size is 64×64 pixels, allowing CU sizes in
50 the range of 64×64 to 8×8 pixels. The PU is the basic entity in intra-prediction that takes
51 the same size of its CU, and only for the smallest CU size (8×8), it can be also split into
52 4×4 sub-PUs. Consequently, the PUs can cover the widest range of sizes from 64×64 to
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4x4 pixels. Finally, the TUs can be partitioned and transformed using a tree structure, termed as Residual Quad Tree (RQT), with a maximum of three depth levels, allowing TU sizes from 32x32 to 4x4.

Intra-prediction achieves optimal coding performance by using an exhaustive evaluation over the 35 prediction modes, and all possible partitions sizes from 64x64 to 4x4, which means the evaluation of 341 different blocks by CTU.

HEVC exploits the high spatial correlation between PU pixels and the pixels from the top-row and left-column of the neighboring PUs. Those samples, denoted as P_{ref} , are used for the construction of the directional predictors. Detailed information on intra-prediction coding, can be found in [13].

The intra-prediction modes include two non-directional modes, namely *DC* and *Planar*, which achieve a high efficiency performance in smooth gradient areas, and 33 angular modes for image areas with edge patterns. The HEVC angular modes are defined with a 1/32 of fractional precision between two-integer pixel positions of P_{ref} , and these are clustered in 16 horizontal modes, named from H_2 to H_{17} , and 17 vertical modes, named from as V_{18} to V_{34} .

The angular predictors can be also classified in two categories: the first one is composed by the five modes, which orientations match with the integer position of the reference pixels. We called this first category as Integer Position Modes (IPM). These are the horizontal H_{10} , the vertical V_{26} and the three diagonal modes: H_2 , V_{18} and V_{34} . The second category includes the rest of the modes with orientation falling between two references samples, and therefore the predictors are computed by the interpolation of the two nearest P_{ref} samples. We named this second category as Fractional Position Modes (FPM).

Table I collects the details of the 33 angular modes, denoted as M_i , where r_i is the angular mode orientation, which is defined as a rational slope $r = r_y/r_x$, and θ_i is the orientation angle, such as $\theta_i = \arctan(r_i)$. As can be noted, the IPMs have an integer slope r_i , meanwhile the FPMs have a non-integer slope r_i . Lines with rational slopes, are

commonly used in digital images processing, favours its definition in the discrete space \mathbb{Z}^2 , denoted as integer lattice, $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. Given a continuous line with rational slope $r = r_y/r_x$, it can be represented by (1),

$$y = r \cdot x + d, \forall r \in \mathbb{Q} \quad (1)$$

Just if 'x' takes integer values multiples of r_x , that is $x = k \cdot r_x, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}$, 'y' reaches an integer position in \mathcal{A} . Accordingly, the distance between two points with integer positions belonging to a line with rational slope r_i , is determined by the r_x, r_y parameters.

As can be observed in Table I, the FPM modes, $H_3, V_{19}, H_9, V_{25}, H_{11}, V_{27}, H_{17}$ and V_{33} have a rational slopes of $\pm m/16$ and $\pm 16/m \forall m = 1, 13$, that means those lines are defined with at least two point in integer position for PU sizes largest of 16×16 , that is 32×32 and 64×64 PU sizes, but not for $16 \times 16, 8 \times 8$ and 4×4 . The other 20 FPM modes in HEVC have a rational slope of $\pm m/32$ and $\pm 32/m \forall m = 5, 9, 13, 17, 21$, thus their lines are defined with two points in integer position for PU sizes largest of 32×32 , which only applies for the 64×64 PU size.

Table I. Orientations and slopes of angular modes in HEVC

Mode M_i	Angle Θ_i	Slope r_i	Mode M_i	Angle Θ_i	Slope r_i
H_2	$5\pi/4$	-1	V_{18}	$3\pi/4$	1
H_3	$39\pi/32$	-13/16	V_{19}	$23\pi/32$	16/13
H_4	$38\pi/32$	-21/32	V_{20}	$22\pi/32$	32/21
H_5	$37\pi/32$	-17/32	V_{21}	$21\pi/32$	32/17
H_6	$36\pi/32$	-13/32	V_{22}	$20\pi/32$	32/13
H_7	$35\pi/32$	-9/32	V_{23}	$19\pi/32$	32/9
H_8	$34\pi/32$	-5/32	V_{24}	$18\pi/32$	32/5
H_9	$33\pi/32$	-1/16	V_{25}	$17\pi/32$	16/1
H_{10}	π	0	V_{26}	$\pi/2$	∞
H_{11}	$31\pi/32$	1/16	V_{27}	$15\pi/32$	-16/1
H_{12}	$30\pi/32$	5/32	V_{28}	$14\pi/32$	-32/5
H_{13}	$29\pi/32$	9/32	V_{29}	$13\pi/32$	-32/9
H_{14}	$28\pi/32$	13/32	V_{30}	$12\pi/32$	-32/13
H_{15}	$27\pi/32$	17/32	V_{31}	$11\pi/32$	-32/17
H_{16}	$26\pi/32$	21/32	V_{32}	$10\pi/32$	-32/21
H_{17}	$25\pi/32$	13/16	V_{33}	$9\pi/32$	-16/13
			V_{34}	$\pi/4$	-1

With the aim of reducing the computational complexity, the HEVC reference model [14], version HM16.6, implements a low complexity intra-prediction algorithm, which is based on *Piao et al.*'s scheme [15]. This algorithm workflow is performed by means of two

1 processes that are repeated for each PU , the Rough Mode Decision (RMD) and the RDO.
2 The RMD model evaluates the 35 prediction modes computing a low complexity *Lagrange*
3 cost function (J_{HAD}), which uses the *Sum of Absolute Hadamard Transformed Differences*
4 (SATD). The N modes with lowest J_{HAD} cost are selected as candidate modes to be
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6 evaluated by the RDO stage, being N equal to 3 for the PU sizes of 64x64, 32x32 and
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8 16x16, and N is equal to 8 for others PU sizes. The RDO carry out the exhaustive PU
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10 encoding and decoding, in order to compute Lagrange J_{mode} cost, and the mode with the
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12 lowest cost is selected as the optimal prediction mode for each PU .
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18 **III. RELATED WORK**

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21 Recently, many proposals have been presented by the research community in order to
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23 alleviate the high computational burden of the HEVC intra-coding, avoiding the exhaustive
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25 evaluation of the full number of size-mode combinations through the rate distortion
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27 optimization stage.
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31 According to the algorithm approach, proposals can be classified into three categories.
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33 The first one evaluates all the prediction modes but reduces the number of CU sizes
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35 required to be checked by both the RMD and the RDO stages, mostly by limiting the depth
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37 of the CTU tree, and thus they are commonly named as *tree pruning* or *early termination*
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39 algorithms. The second category reduces the number of angular prediction modes to be
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41 checked for the RMD stage as well as, eventually, the number of candidates in the rate
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43 distortion optimization stage, mainly based on content features. The last category combines
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45 both approaches, mainly reducing the number of directional modes and the candidate CU
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47 sizes to be checked.
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51 In the first group, the proposals can be classified into two different sub-categories. The
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53 first sub-category contains those in which the partitioning decision is taken exclusively on
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55 the basis of the RD cost value of the different CU sizes [16][17][18]. The approaches in the
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57 second sub-category [19][20] mainly use the same schema, but the optimal CTU
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59 partitioning prediction is based on some content features extracted from the CUs.
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Most popular approaches in the second group are based on pixel gradient detection in the spatial domain using the Sobel filter, followed by the Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG) computation. In [21] few directional modes are selected as candidates for the RDO based on HOG. Chen *et al.* in [22] uses a 2x2 filter to select the strong primary gradient direction of the PU, introducing the conception of non-parametric approach to estimate the distribution density of the gradient histogram. Yan *et al.* in [23] apply a pixel-based edge detection algorithm based on the sum of absolute differences in the angle of the prediction modes by using a 2-taps interpolation method. In [24], a reduction of intra-modes was proposed using five different filters to detect the dominant edge of the 4x4 PUs, and a set of 11 prediction modes closer to the dominant edge are evaluated. The Yao *et al.* [25] proposal reduces the number of prediction modes to be evaluated to eleven modes or only two modes, *DC* and *Planar*, depending on the dominant edge assent standard deviation.

Finally, the proposals presented by [26] and [27] fall in the last group. Shen [26] suggested a fast-partitioning decision algorithm that uses the correlation of the content and the optimal CTU tree depth, limiting the minimum and maximum depth levels. The algorithm is based on the observed evidence that small CUs tend to be chosen for rich textured regions, whereas large CUs are chosen for homogeneous regions. It computes a depth predictor by using the neighboring tree blocks and two early terminations for prediction modes based on the statistics of neighboring blocks and the RD cost of the candidates. The authors reported a 21% time reduction with a rate penalty of 1.7%. By using a similar approach, the fast intra-prediction algorithm presented in [27] is based on the RD cost difference between the first and second candidate modes computed in the RMD stage, and this reduces the number of RDO candidates from N to one mode (Best Candidate) or three modes (Best Candidate, DC, and MPM). In addition, if the RD cost of the best mode of the RDO stage is under a threshold, the algorithm decides to apply an early termination pruning to the tree to avoid the evaluation of lower CU sizes. The algorithm achieves a computational complexity reduction of 30.5% with an average performance drop of 1.2%.

IV. UNIFIED ARCHITECTURE FOR FAST HEVC INTRA-PREDICTION CODING

As mentioned in Section II, the HEVC intra-prediction can achieve a high level of performance at the expenses of a huge computational burden due to the high number of combinations involved in the intra-prediction process, comprising the evaluation of all possible prediction modes and the full range of CU sizes. With the aim of reducing the HEVC intra-prediction complexity, this section presents our *Unified Architecture* to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD). This approach combines, in a first stage, a *Fast Partitioning Decision* (FPD) algorithm for the CTU coding decision based on decision trees, which are trained using ML techniques, and in a second stage, a *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD) algorithm, based on a novel texture orientation detection algorithm.

A. Stage 1: The Fast Partitioning Decision (FPD) Algorithm

1. Observations and Motivation

The first stage of the *Unified Architecture* proposed in this paper is derived from the analysis of the computational complexity of the intra-prediction algorithm implemented in the HM reference software [14]. In some preliminary tests where one sequence from each class of the JCT-VC test sequences [28] have been encoded using the HM 16.6 reference model, the computing time of each intra-prediction stage has been collected. The results for two QPs, QP22 and QP37, showing that the complexity of the RMD and RDO stages makes up over 80% of the total intra-prediction computation, and the remainder of the time is spent by the RQT stage and other auxiliary tasks. This fact has motivated the design of our FPD algorithm, which replaces the brute force scheme used in the HEVC through the RMD and RDO, with a low complexity algorithm based on a fast CU size classifier, which is previously trained using ML methodology. The classifier selects a sub-optimal CTU partitioning, thus avoiding the exhaustive evaluation of all available CU sizes.

The FPD approach proposed is based on the fact that the CU partitioning decision can be taken using the local CU features, considering that there exists a strong correlation between the optimal partitioning size and the texture complexity of the CU. It is well-known that homogeneous blocks achieve best performance when being encoded by large block sizes. Otherwise, highly textured blocks can be efficiently encoded by using small sizes that adjust their size to the details of the image.

The proposed algorithm uses a binary classifier based on a decision tree with two classes, *Split* and *Non-Split*, in each top-three depths of the CTU tree. The algorithm starts with the largest CU size, 64x64, and using several attributes of the CU the decision tree takes the partitioning decision.

2. Training Data Set

With the aim of obtaining a training set covering a wide range of content complexities, the *Spatial Information* (SI) and *Temporal Information* (TI) metrics were computed for all JCT-VC test sequences [28], according to the ITU-T P.910 recommendation [29]. Fig. 1 shows the *Spatio-Temporal* (ST) information of the selected training set sequences. Only the first picture of each selected sequence is used to train the classifier, which is considered enough to achieve a high number of representative CTU samples of blocks with homogeneous areas and blocks with highly detailed textured areas.

Fig. 1. ST information of the training sequences.

3. Attribute Selection

The trained sequences were used for the extraction of attributes from the CUs, and they are also encoded with the HM encoder with the aim of achieving the optimal partitioning of each CTU. The CTU partitioning has been obtained for the four distortion levels QP22, QP27, QP32 and QP37 recommended in the Common Test Conditions and Software Reference Configurations (CTCs) by the JCT-VC [28]. That CTU partitioning allows us to classify each CU in a binary class that takes the *Split* or *Non-Split* value.

Many features can be extracted from a CU to describe its content using the first and second order metrics in the spatial domain, such as the *Mean*, *Standard Deviation*, *Skewness*, *Kurtosis*, *Entropy*, *Autocorrelation*, *Inertia*, or *Covariance* [30]. There are also useful attributes describing the CU features, which can be computed in the Fourier domain, such as the DC energy, number of non-zero AC coefficients, or the mean and variance of the AC coefficients. Initially, we extracted a large number of such statistics commonly used in image processing and image classification.

The attribute selection was carried out using the open source WEKA, an effective ML tool [31] that provides a set of tools that use different strategies to rank the usefulness of the attributes, denoted as *Attributes Evaluator*, in conjunction with different search algorithms. Considering both factors, attribute ranking and computational complexity, we finally selected the three attributes from the spatial domain with the best performance in terms of ranking evaluation, which are based on the variance and mean computation of the CU. They are the following: i) the variance of the $2N \times 2N$ CUs, denoted as σ_{2N}^2 , ii) the variance of variances of the four $N \times N$ sub-CUs, denoted as $\sigma^2[\sigma_N^2]$, and, iii) the variance of the means of the four $N \times N$ sub-CUs, denoted as $\sigma^2[\mu_N]$.

In order to reduce the complexity of the variance computation, it is implemented by the variance algorithm named *textbook one-pass* proposed in the Chan *et al.* algorithm [32]. This variance approach does not require passing through the data twice, once to calculate mean and again to compute sum of squares of deviations from mean.

4. Decision Tree Specification

Prior to the training of the decision tree, and considering that it is one of the key factors in ML, we proceeded to the classifier selection. From among several classifiers, C4.5 [33] is a well-known classifier for general-purpose classifying problems [34] as well as for video coding purposes [35]. The most common mechanism for measuring the trained decision tree accuracy is the 10-fold cross-validation process available in WEKA, which provides the prediction error measured in terms of misclassification instances or percentage of Correctly Classified Instances (CCI).

The first node, denoted as *Node64*, is the most critical node because a wrong *Non-Split* decision at the highest partitioning level can cause a 64x64 CTU that should be divided into several smaller CUs not to be split, and therefore the compression efficiency will be reduced. We used 4231 instances for the training of the *Node64* by using the 4231 64x64 of CTUs of the 8 frames used from the 8 test sequences. These instances suffer the well-known imbalance problem because there are significantly more instances belonging to *Split*, by over 80%, than *Non-Split* with just 8% for the QP22. To address the imbalance issue, previously to the training of the decision tree for *Node64*, an unsupervised instance random subsample filter [36] available in WEKA has been applied.

The training results shown that the CCI after the 10-fold cross-validation step for the decision trees of the *Node64* are over 90%, which can be considered a high accuracy classification. The decision tree for *Node64* is shown in Fig. 2. *Node64* is defined with 3 inner nodes, three rules, and one condition for each rule with a specific threshold Th_i ($\forall i = 1,2,3$) that determines the binary decision within the inner nodes.

Node32 processes the split 32x32 CUs from *Node64*, and the decision of *Non-Split* the CUs is taken, forwarding the CUs classified as *Split* to *Node16*, and otherwise sending the *Non-Split* CUs to the intra-prediction stage for an exhaustive evaluation of the 32x32 and 16x16 PU sizes. The total training data set size for this node is 16,924, and, in this case, only the class distribution for the QP22 and QP27 were imbalanced, because there were

significantly more instances belonging to *Split*, by over 60%, than *Non-Split*, with around 30%.

Fig. 2. Decision tree for Node64

Fig. 3. Decision tree for Node32

The training results shown a CCI after the 10-fold cross-validation step for the decision trees of *Node32* are in the range of 83% to 89%, which can still be considered a high accuracy classification. The decision tree for *Node32* is shown in Fig. 3. Based on the *variance* of the 32x32 CUs and the *variance* of the *variances* of their four 16x16 sub-CUs, the *decision tree* classifies each of them in the *Split* or *Non-Split* class. *Node32* is defined

with two inner nodes and one condition for each rule with a specific threshold Th_i ($\forall i = 4,5$) that determines the binary decision within the inner nodes.

Node16 processes the 16x16 CUs split from *Node32*, and a new decision to *Split* or *Non-Split* is taken. The 4,231 CTUs that comprise the data set, belonging to the 8 test sequences, are divided into 16x16 CUs for the *Node16* training, and therefore the total training data set size for this node is 67,696 instances.

The training results obtained after the 10-fold cross-validation step for the decision trees of *Node16* are in the CCI range of 72% to 79%. The *decision tree* for *Node16* is shown in Fig. 4. *Node16* is defined with three inner nodes and one condition for each rule with a specific threshold Th_i ($\forall i = 6, 7, 8$), which determines the binary decision within the inner nodes.

Fig. 4. Decision tree for *Node16*

B. Stage 2: The Fast Mode Decision (FMD) Algorithm

1. Observations and Motivation

Many proposals have been presented in the literature for the fast optimal mode decision in HEVC [21]-[25]. Most of them are based on pixel gradient detection in the spatial domain by computing the gradient of the image using the Sobel filter [37] or other similar filters. This technique has been proved robust when high-energy edges are present in the image,

1 but natural images often have wide areas with weak edges, or even no edges, so this
2 approach can be inefficient for the intra-prediction mode decision.
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4 This fact has motivated the algorithm presented for this second stage of our *Unified*
5 *Architecture*, denoted as *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD) algorithm. In this paper, a novel
6 texture orientation detection algorithm is proposed, which computes the *Mean Directional*
7 *Variance* (MDV) using a *Sliding Window* (SW), along a set of *co-lines* with rational slopes,
8 denoted as MDV-SW. The key point of the proposed algorithm is based on the hypothesis
9 that pixel correlation is maximum in the texture orientation, and consequently the variance
10 computed in that direction will obtain a low value compared with the variance computed
11 in other directions. Another noteworthy feature of this proposal is the use of a set of rational
12 slopes, which are exclusively defined in an integer position of the discrete lattice Λ , thus
13 no pixel interpolation is required. Moreover, it was observed that there exists a strong
14 dependence between the optimal mode selected by the RDO and the distortion applied, set
15 by the QP parameter. Therefore, the directional variance computation for each $N \times N$ PU is
16 expanded to $(N + 1) \times (N + 1)$ window, thus the neighbouring pixels used as reference
17 samples for the construction of the predictor are also included in the calculation of the
18 directional variance.
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37 In order to reduce the computational complexity of the gradient detection, we need to
38 define lines where their points are located in the integer position of lattice $\Lambda \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, so that
39 we can describe the problem of the discretization of a direction in the discrete space \mathbb{Z}^2 as
40 the sub-sampling of an integer lattice.
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48 2. Sub-sampling of Integer Lattice

49 The Directional Variance metric described in [38] uses the traditional definition of “*digital*
50 *line*” for the discrete space \mathbb{Z}^2 , such that $L(r, n)$ is a *digital line* with rational slope r , $\forall r$
51 $\in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$, meaning that every pixel with position $(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ is associated
52 exclusively to one *digital line*, defined as:
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$$60 y = [r \cdot x] + n \quad \forall x, n \in \mathbb{Z}, \forall |r| \leq 1, \text{ or} \quad (2)$$

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$$x = \lfloor y/r \rfloor + n \quad \forall y, n \in \mathbb{Z}, \forall |r| > 1 \quad (3)$$

Therefore, for each rational slope $r = r_y/r_x \quad \forall r_x, r_y \in \mathbb{Z}$ a set of integers, denoted as n , can be found, which define the *digital lines* $L(r, n)$. *Digital lines* have been widely used in different fields, including image processing, image coding and artificial vision, among others. However, they do not provide enough accuracy for gradient detection in images or pixel blocks with small size. Fig. 5(a) depicts an example of an image composed by four equally spaced bars (grey bars) with a slope of $1/3$, where we have plot the set of *digital lines* with same slope $L(1/3, n)$ covering the image. As can be observed, although the *digital lines* and the plotted bars have the same slope, the *digital lines* aren't representing the orientation of the bars with high accuracy. There are some *digital lines* which only two of each three pixels belong to the bar, and the other *digital lines* two of each three pixels are out of the bars but they have a pixel into the bar, reducing the pixels correlation along the *digital lines*.

This is due to the *digital lines* are not straight, instead they are covering an area whose width depends on the slope factors (r_x, r_y) . Fig. 5(b) shows an example of two *digital lines*, $L(1/3, n)$ and $L(3/4, n)$, where the *digital line* areas have been shaded and the *digital line* width is denoted as μ . Using simple trigonometric functions can be demonstrated that $\mu = r_y(r_x - 1)/\sqrt{r_x^2 + r_y^2}$, and consequently μ increases with the r_x, r_y increasing, as is shown in Fig. 5(b) for rational slopes of $1/3$ and $3/4$. This feature of the *digital lines*, their width, limits the orientation detection accuracy of the *digital lines*, mainly for directions represented by rational slopes that requires high r_x, r_y factors.

For this reason, the concept of a down-sampling lattice in two-dimensional space described in [39] has been used, together with the *co-lines* definition used in lattice theory [40]. According to [39], in a 2D system an integer lattice Λ can be obtained by down-sampling in two directions \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2 of the cubic integer lattice \mathbb{Z}^2 .

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Fig. 5. (a) Example of four bars with orientation $r = 1/3$, and the set of digital lines $L(1/3, n)$.
(b) Area covered by two digital lines with rational slopes of $1/3$ and $3/4$.

Hence, the sublattice $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{Z}^2$ can be formally represented by a non-singular 2×2 integer matrix, denoted as *sub-sampling matrix* or *generator matrix*, \mathbf{M}_A , such that $d_{x1}, d_{y1}, d_{x2}, d_{y2} \in \mathbb{Z}$, that is:

$$\mathbf{M}_A = [r_1 \ r_2] = \begin{bmatrix} d_{x1} & d_{x2} \\ d_{y1} & d_{y2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The use of the rational slopes as sub-sampling directions in \mathbf{M}_A , in their vector form $\mathbf{d}_1 = [d_{x1}, d_{y1}]^T$ and $\mathbf{d}_2 = [d_{x2}, d_{y2}]^T$, makes it possible to obtain a sub-lattice Λ which describes the points of the line with slopes d_1 and d_2 , and thus it facilitates the variance computation along those orientations. Lattice theory states that given a *generator matrix* \mathbf{M}_A , the lattice \mathbb{Z}^2 is partitioned into $|\det(\mathbf{M}_A)|$ number of cosets of the lattice Λ that are shifted versions of the sub-lattice Λ . Each coset can be obtained by a shifting vector $\mathbf{s}_k = [s_{kx}, s_{ky}]^T \forall k = 0, 1, \dots, \det(\mathbf{M}_A) - 1$. In [40] the concept of *co-line*, denoted as $CL_{S_k}(r, n)$, is introduced, and it is defined as the intersection of a k^{th} coset in lattice Λ and a *digital line* $L(r, n)$. Therefore, the pixels (x, y) belonging to the *co-lines* with slope d_1

and d_2 can be obtained by the linear combination of both vectors $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \forall c_1, c_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$, such that,

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = c_1 \begin{bmatrix} d_{x1} \\ d_{y1} \end{bmatrix} + c_2 \begin{bmatrix} d_{x2} \\ d_{y2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} s_{kx} \\ s_{ky} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Our proposal computes the variance along the pixels of the *co-lines* with a set of rational slopes r_i , which can be obtained using the generator matrix \mathbf{M}_A where any couple of rational slopes $r_1 = r_{y1}/r_{x1}$ and $r_2 = r_{y2}/r_{x2}$ can be used as vector directions \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2 in \mathbf{M}_A . Equation (5) can be rewritten as two independent equations using the r_1 and r_2 slopes, such as;

$$x = c_1 r_{x1} + c_2 r_{x2} + s_{kx} \quad (6)$$

$$y = c_1 r_{y1} + c_2 r_{y2} + s_{ky} \quad (7)$$

By isolating for the variable c_1 from (6) and substituting it into (7), the expression of the *co-lines* with orientation r_1 is obtained as is shown in (8) and (9), $\forall c_2 \in \mathbb{Z}, k = 0, \dots, \det(\mathbf{M}_A) - 1$.

$$y = r_1 x + n \quad \forall |r_1| > 1, \quad n = c_2(r_{y2} - r_1 r_{x2}) - r_1 s_{kx} + s_{ky}, \quad \text{or} \quad (8)$$

$$x = y/r_1 + n \quad \forall |r_1| \leq 1, \quad n = c_2(r_{x2} - r_{y2}/r_1) - s_{ky}/r_1 + s_{kx} \quad (9)$$

With the aim of clarifying this process for *co-lines* with slope r_1 , Fig. 6(a) shows an example using the directional vectors $\mathbf{r}_1=[1, 2]^T$ and $\mathbf{r}_2=[2, -1]^T$. Given that $|\det(\mathbf{M}_A)| = 5$, there are five cosets determined by the shifting vectors $\mathbf{s}_0 = [-1, 0], \mathbf{s}_1 = [0, 1], \mathbf{s}_2 = [0, 0], \mathbf{s}_3 = [0, -1], \mathbf{s}_4 = [1, 0]$, and those are represented by the dotted, black, grey, white, and lined points, respectively. Setting $c_2 = 0$ we obtain the expression of the *co-lines* for the first five cosets, and setting $c_2 = 1$ the next five *co-lines* are likewise obtained, which are depicted as solid lines and dashed lines respectively in Fig. 6(a).

Following the same reasoning, the expression of the *co-lines* with orientation r_2 is obtained by isolating for the variable c_2 from (8) and substituting it into (9), as is shown (10) and (11), $\forall c_1 \in \mathbb{Z}, k = 0, \dots, \det(\mathbf{M}_A) - 1$.

$$y = r_2 x + n \quad \forall |r_2| > 1, \quad n = c_1(r_{y1} - r_2 r_{x1}) - r_2 s_{kx} + s_{ky}, \quad \text{or} \quad (10)$$

$$x = y/r_2 + n \quad \forall |r_2| \leq 1, \quad n = c_1(r_{x1} - r_{y1}/r_2) - s_{ky}/r_2 + s_{kx} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 6. (a) Example of *co-lines* and their respective cosets for the slope \mathbf{r}_1 , using as direction vectors $\mathbf{r}_1=[1,2]^T$ and $\mathbf{r}_2=[2,-1]^T$ of the subsampling matrix \mathbf{M}_Λ . (b) Example of *co-lines* and their respective cosets for the slope \mathbf{r}_2 , using as direction vectors $\mathbf{r}_1=[1,2]^T$ and $\mathbf{r}_2=[2,-1]^T$ of the subsampling matrix \mathbf{M}_Λ .

Fig. 6(b) shows the same example of Fig. 6(a) but now for the expression of the *co-lines* with slope \mathbf{r}_2 . Now, setting $c_1 = 1$ the expression of the *co-lines* for the first five cosets are obtained, and the next set of five *co-lines* are equally obtained by setting $c_1 = 2$, which are depicted as solid lines and dashed lines respectively.

As can be observed in Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b), the distance between two consecutive pixels belonging to one *co-line* is always the same, and its position is free of any type of interpolation process. Consequently, the *co-lines* are available to represent the geometrical orientation with highest accuracy than the traditional *digital lines*, particularly for the small size blocks, as is demanded in HEVC.

3. Selection of the Co-lines Orientation

The decision of the *co-lines* orientations that best match with the modes directionality in HEVC is one of the key points of our approach. In order to estimate the dominant texture orientation in each PU, twelve rational slopes r_i , ($\forall i = 0, \dots, 11$) have been selected. Four of them with the same slope as the IPM modes, that is the horizontal, vertical and two diagonal orientations (the diagonal H_2 and V_{34} are considered the same in terms of slope), and the other eight slopes are defined with slopes close to some of the FPM modes, but with rational slopes of $\pm 1/2$, $\pm 1/4$, ± 2 , and ± 4 . Table II summarizes the set of six *generator matrices* \mathbf{M}_{Λ_i} , the vector directions used for the integer lattice sub-sampling, and the respective cosets defined by $\det(\mathbf{M}_{\Lambda_i})$. The chosen orientations have a maximum slope factor of 4 instead of 32, as the HEVC modes have (Table I).

Table II. Six generator matrixes defining the twelve rational slopes and the respective cosets

\mathbf{M}_{Λ_i}	Vector directions	Generator matrix	Cosets
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_0}	r_3, r_9	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	1
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_1}	r_0, r_6	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	2
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_2}	r_1, r_7	$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$	5
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_3}	r_5, r_{11}	$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$	5
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_4}	r_2, r_8	$\begin{bmatrix} 4 & 1 \\ -1 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$	17
\mathbf{M}_{Λ_5}	r_4, r_{10}	$\begin{bmatrix} 4 & 1 \\ 1 & -4 \end{bmatrix}$	17

Consequently, there are always two points that determine a *co-line* with rational slope r_i , except for the smaller PU size of 4×4 and the largest slopes ($r = 1/4$ and $r = 4$), which use a pixel of a neighbouring blocks. Fig. 7 shows the set of twelve rational slopes.

With the aim of comparing the orientations of the selected slopes with the HEVC modes' directionality, Fig. 8 depicts both, the 33 angular intra-prediction modes defined in HEVC (grey solid lines) and the twelve proposed *co-lines* with rational slope (blue dashed lines), which have been chosen for the analysis of the dominant gradient.

Fig. 7. Co-lines r_0 to r_{11} selected to compute of directional variance.

As can be observed, the co-lines $r_0, r_3, r_6,$ and r_9 overlap the angular modes $H_2, V_{10}, V_{18}, V_{26}$ and V_{34} , thus such modes can be estimated with high accuracy from respective co-lines. The co-lines with slopes r_1, r_5, r_7 and r_{11} , mostly overlap the angular modes $H_5, V_{15}, V_{21},$ and V_{31} , so these co-lines can be also considered as a good estimation of the co-located modes.

Fig. 8. Set of angular intra predictions in HEVC (grey), and the co-lines defined with rational slopes r_0 to r_{11} (dotted blue lines) for the dominant gradient analysis.

Finally, the four *co-lines* with slopes r_2, r_4, r_8 and r_{10} , are located near the middle of two modes H_7 and H_8 for the slope r_2 , H_{12} and H_{13} for the slope r_4 , V_{23} and V_{24} for the slope r_8 , and V_{28} and V_{29} for the slope r_{10} .

With the aim of considering the remaining angular modes that are not covered by each of the twelve proposed slopes r_i , twelve classes denoted as C_i have been defined. Each class selects a set of candidate modes M_i on the left and right side of the respective rational slopes r_i . Table III shows the features of the proposed *co-lines* r_i . It should be noted that the *co-line* r_0 is the only one slope, which selects four angular modes in its class. This is due to modes H_2 and V_{34} of HEVC being the same in terms of orientation, so the two horizontal H_2, H_3 , and the two vertical V_{33}, V_{34} modes, are selected as candidates.

Based on empirical simulations, one candidate mode on the left and right side of each class has been added for the smaller PU sizes of 8×8 and 4×4 , except for the horizontal r_3 and vertical, r_6 , slopes. This is motivated by the fact that the *co-lines* in those block sizes with no Cartesian orientations are defined by a low number of pixels, and the accuracy of the orientation detection is also lower. In addition, the two non-angular modes, *DC* and *Planar* are included as candidates for all the classes, because they match quite well with weak edge images.

Table III. Slope, angle and candidate modes assigned to defined *co-lines*

Co-line	Θ_i	Slope (r_y/r_x)	PU Class (C_i)	Candidates modes M_i for PU ₆₄ , PU ₃₂ , PU ₁₆	Additional Candidates M_i for PU ₈ , PU ₄
r_0	$5\pi/4$	-1/1	I	H_2, H_3, V_{33}, V_{34}	H_4, V_{32}
r_1	$8\pi/7$	-1/2	II	H_4, H_5, H_6	H_3, H_7
r_2	$27\pi/25$	-1/4	III	H_7, H_8	H_6, H_9
r_3	π	0	IV	H_9, H_{10}, H_{11}	H_8, H_{12}
r_4	$23\pi/25$	1/4	V	H_{12}, H_{13}	H_{11}, H_{14}
r_5	$6\pi/7$	1/2	VI	H_{14}, H_{15}, H_{16}	H_{13}, H_{17}
r_6	$3\pi/4$	1/1	VII	H_{17}, V_{18}, V_{19}	H_{16}, V_{20}
r_7	$9\pi/14$	2/1	VIII	V_{20}, V_{21}, V_{22}	V_{19}, V_{23}
r_8	$29\pi/50$	4/1	IX	V_{23}, V_{24}	V_{22}, V_{25}
r_9	$\pi/2$	∞	X	V_{25}, V_{26}, V_{27}	V_{24}, V_{28}
r_{10}	$21\pi/50$	-4/1	XI	V_{28}, V_{29}	V_{27}, V_{30}
r_{11}	$5\pi/14$	-2/1	XII	V_{30}, V_{31}, V_{32}	V_{29}, V_{33}

4. Computation of Mean Directional Variance (MDV) along Co-lines

Cumulative variance along *digital lines* is proposed in [38], which is proven as an efficient metric for texture orientation detection in images with large size. However, due to the constraints imposed by factors such as the PU sizes, the high density of the intra-prediction modes in HEVC, and the need to reduce the encoder's computational burden, the following modifications and novel features are proposed:

1. The variance is computed along the *co-lines* according to (8) to (11), instead of using the *digital lines* expression.
2. In order to reduce the computational complexity of the variance, an approximation of the variance, denoted *textbook one-pass* algorithm, proposed by *Chan et al.* in [32] is used. Eq. (12) shows the directional variance expression using the *textbook one-pass* approach, $p_j(r_i, n)$ being the pixels belonging to $CL(r_i, n)$, and N the number of pixels of the n th *co-line* with slope r_i :

$$\sigma^2[CL(r_i, n)] = \frac{1}{N} \left[\sum_{j=0}^N p_j^2(r_i, n) - \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{j=0}^N p_j(r_i, n) \right)^2 \right] \quad (12)$$

3. Finally, instead of calculating the cumulative variance of the *digital lines* as is proposed in [38], the MDV is computed as the average of the individual variances obtained along the L *co-lines* with the same r_i orientation, as is shown in (13).

$$MDV(r_i) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{n=1}^L \sigma^2[CL(r_i, n)] \quad (13)$$

5. Computation of Mean Directional Variance Using Sliding Window (MDV-SW)

As has been described previously, the MDV is computed for each PU using the pixels of *co-segments* $CS_m(r_i, n)$ belonging to that PU in a scalable manner. However, the angular modes in HEVC intra-prediction use as reference sample the neighboring pixels of decoded PUs, denoted as $PU_d(x, y)$, which have been previously distorted by the quantification factor QP. Based on empirical simulations, we observed the strong dependence between the optimal mode selected by the RDO and the QP parameter, especially for high QP values, which cause a strong smoothing of the reference pixels, thus the correlation between

the reference samples and the PU's pixels that are not yet distorted can be modified. Consequently, an enhancement to the MDV algorithm is proposed in this sub-section. The main idea of this approach is to expand the window of the MDV computation for a $N \times N$ PU to a window of $(N + 1) \times (N + 1)$ pixels, overlapping the left column and top row of the window with the left and top decoded pixels of the neighbouring PUs. Fig. 9(a) depicts an example of the computation of the MDV for a 4×4 PU(i, j) along the slope r_6 , where the reference samples (P_{ref}) belonging to decoded PUs (PU_d) are lined. As can be observed, five *co-segments* with lengths of 2, 3 and 4 pixels are defined for such slope. Fig. 9(b) presents the new MDV approach, where the new $(N + 1) \times (N + 1)$ window allows the MDV computation using the reference pixels from the neighbouring PUs, and two new *co-segments* are now available.

Fig. 9. (a) Example of MDV computation of 4×4 PU. (b) Example of MDV-SW computation over expanded window for a 4×4 PUs. (c) Example of MDV-SW using overlapped windows for the evaluation of 4×4 PUs

Accordingly, the MDV is computed in five overlapping window sizes of 65×65 , 33×33 , 17×17 , 9×9 and 5×5 pixels, thus this novel approach is named *Mean Directional Variance with Sliding Window* (MDV-SW). Fig. 9(c) illustrates an example of the MDV-SW computation of four consecutive 4×4 PUs $\{PU(i + k, j + l) \mid \forall k, l = 0, 1\}$, showing that the sliding windows are overlapping each other, in order to capture the neighboring reference samples.

The MDV-SW implementation needs a slight computation increase compared with the MDV due to the extended window size and therefore the border pixels are being computed twice for the adjacent PUs.

C. The Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision Architecture (FPMD)

Finally, this sub-section presents the proposed unified architecture to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD). This approach combines the FPD algorithm proposed in Sub-section IV.A, and the FMD algorithm proposed in Sub-section IV.B. The FPMD algorithm presented in this paper achieves a considerable complexity reduction of over 67%, at the expense of a slight penalty in terms of rate increase, due to sub-optimal partitioning and the mode decision given by the FPMD.

The architecture of the FPMD is depicted in Fig. 10, which shows the new functional algorithms introduced by FPMD shaded in grey. The FPMD workflow works at the CTU level, as was described in Sub-section IV.A, evaluating the CTU attributes that are used by the *decision trees* in the CTU classifier stage, selecting the different PU sizes. With the aim of organizing the set of PUs that partition the CTU, a *Partition Map* is arranged by depth levels ($\forall d = 0, \dots, 4$). For each d level, the k PUs ($PU_{d,k}$) belonging to that depth level is recorded in a list.

Intra-prediction is computed by the evaluation of all PUs included in the *Partition Map* lists, which are processed in depth level order. Following the fast partitioning algorithm described in Sub-section IV.A, for every $PU_{d,k}$, the four sub-PUs ($PU_{d+1,4k+i} \forall i = 0, \dots, 3$) are also evaluated by the RMD, RDO and RQT stages. Consequently, five evaluations are always performed for each element of the *Partition Map*.

Then, the MDV-SW algorithm is run for each PU in the *Partition Map*, and it is classified by a class C_i , which includes a set of 3 or 4 candidate angular modes in addition to the two non-directional modes, *DC* and *Planar*, as was described in Sub-section IV.B.

Those modes are arranged in a *Mode List*, and they will be the only modes that will be evaluated by the RMD, instead of the 35 modes evaluated by the original RMD stage of the HM reference software.

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Fig. 10. Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision (FPMD) algorithm proposed.

Because of the RMD process, a set of three candidate modes is selected to be checked by the RDO stage, and the mode with the lowest cost is selected to be further evaluated by the RQT, which selects the optimal TU size. Finally, by comparing the cost of the $PU_{d,k}$ with the sum of the costs of the four sub-PUs, the best option *Non-Split* $PU_{d,k}$ or the four *Split* $PU_{d+1,4k+i} (\forall i = 0, ..3)$ is selected.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

With the aim of evaluating the proposed *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD) algorithm, the FPD algorithm and the FMD algorithm for Intra-prediction in HEVC were implemented in the HEVC HM 16.6 reference software [14]. The non-modified HM 16.6 reference software was used as anchor by using the same test sequences and encoding parameters. The simulations were independently run for the three node configurations of the FPD algorithm, in order to report the results by applying the algorithm in a scalable way, starting with solely *Node64*, then *Node64+Node32*, and finally *Node64+Node32+Node16*. FMD was evaluated based on the MDV and MDV-SW proposals. Then, all combinations of FPD+MDV-SW (*Node64+MDV-SW*, *Node64+Node32+MDV-SW* and *Node64+Node32+Node16+MDV-SW*), were also activated to show the simulation results for the FPMD algorithm, which combines both proposals.

A. Encoding Parameters and Metrics

The experiments were conducted under the “*Common Test Conditions and Software Reference Configurations*” (CTC) recommended by the JCT-VC [28] for the “*All-Intra*” mode configuration, and the Main profile (AI-Main). That recommendation specifies the use of four QPs (QP22, QP27, QP32 and QP37) and a set of 22 test sequences classified in five classes, named from A to E, which cover wide range of resolutions and frame rates. All the sequences use 4:2:0 chroma subsampling and a bit-depth of 8 bits.

The algorithm performance was evaluated in terms of *Computational Complexity Reduction* (CCR) and *Rate-Distortion* (RD) performance, and both of them were compared to the HM results. For the CCR measure, the *Time Saving* metric was computed following (14):

$$Time\ Saving(\%) = \frac{Enc.\ Time\ (HM16.6) - Enc.\ Time(Prop)}{Enc.\ Time\ (HM16.6)} \cdot 100 \quad (14)$$

Concerning the RD performance, the average *Peak Signal to Noise Ratio* (PSNR) metric was calculated for each luma (Y_PSNR) and chroma components (U_PSNR , V_PSNR). The YUV_PSNRs for the four QPs were used for the computation of the RD performance by using the *Bjontegaard Delta-Rate* metric ($BD\text{-}Rate$) defined by ITU [41] and recommended in the CTC [28].

In order to obtain the increase in the $BD\text{-}rate$ and the increase in the *Time Saving* introduced by the fast mode decision algorithm when it is combined in the architecture of each node, the ΔBD_{rate} and $\Delta T.Saving$ metrics are also used, following (15) and (16), and where $N = 64, 64 + 32, 64 + 32 + 16$:

$$\Delta BD_{rate} = BD_{rate_{Node_N}} - BD_{rate_{Node_N+MDV-SW}} \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta T.Saving = T.Saving_{Node_N} - T.Saving_{Node_N+MDV-SW} \quad (16)$$

B. Simulation Results

Table IV shows the experimental results of the FPD algorithm compared with the HM 16.6 reference software. It can be observed that for the *Node64* implementation, all the sequences achieve a negligible 0.1% penalty in terms of $BD\text{-}Rate$, and an average time saving of around 12%. The results for the *Node64+Node32* decision tree implementation reports much better time savings over 29%, and a bit rate increase lower than 1%. Finally, the overall algorithm (*Node64+Node32+Node16*) shows a computational reduction of over 53%, increasing the bit rate penalty by around 2.2%. It should be noted that we used only eight frames for training the decision tree, which is a 0.081% of the total frames that comprises 22 simulated sequences (9,780 frames). The overall experimental results confirm that the FPD algorithm proposed can reduce the computational complexity of HEVC intra-picture prediction by over 53% with a slight bit rate increase, favoring real-time software and hardware implementation.

Table IV. Performance results of the Fast Partitioning Decision (FPD) Algorithm

Classification	Sequence	Frames	N64		N64+N32		N64+N32+N16	
			T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)	T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)	T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)
Class A (2560x1600)	Traffic	150	11.60	0.0	29.39	0.9	56.61	1.6
	PeopleOnStreet	150	12.19	0.0	28.03	0.6	50.09	1.1
Class B (1920x1080)	BasketballDrive	500	14.36	0.2	36.87	2.4	59.19	3.1
	BQTerrace	600	14.15	0.1	30.96	0.8	52.57	1.3
	Cactus	500	13.18	0.1	29.77	1.0	56.95	2.1
	Kimono	240	15.43	0.1	33.90	5.1	62.05	5.3
	ParkScene	240	14.51	0.0	30.74	0.9	58.75	1.6
Class C (832x480)	BasketballDrill	500	15.4	0.0	27.63	0.5	53.50	2.3
	BQMall	600	10.27	0.0	26.88	0.8	50.76	2.5
	PartyScene	500	10.89	0.0	22.08	0.1	45.48	2.1
	RaceHorses	300	10.18	0.0	26.41	0.7	53.14	1.7
Class D (416x240)	BasketballPass	500	10.25	0.0	23.54	0.6	45.66	2.1
	BQSquare	600	5.98	0.0	21.11	0.3	35.61	1.1
	BlowingBubbles	500	8.82	0.0	18.58	0.0	40.55	1.7
Class E (128x720)	RaceHorses	300	6.80	0.0	19.75	0.4	43.20	1.8
	FourPeople	600	8.13	0.0	33.88	0.8	56.64	2.0
	Johnny	600	12.48	0.3	45.54	3.4	63.00	4.4
	KristenAndSara	600	26.81	0.3	44.39	1.7	61.19	2.6
Class A			11.89	0.00	28.71	0.75	53.35	1.35
Class B			14.32	0.10	32.44	2.04	57.90	2.68
Class C			10.40	0.00	25.75	0.53	50.72	2.15
Class D			7.43	0.00	20.74	0.33	41.25	1.68
Class E			18.22	0.20	41.27	1.97	60.28	3.00
AVERAGE			12.42	0.1	29.82	1.2	53.08	2.2

Table V shows the simulation results for the novel FMD algorithm based on the MDV and MDV-SW proposals compared with the HM 16.6 reference software. As can be observed, with MDV-SW scheme the average time saving has been reduced to a 29.7%, regarding the bit rate penalty, it should be noted the average *BD-rate* is 0.4%.

Table VI reports the simulation results individualized for each possible combination, for the final *Unified Architecture* proposed based on FPMD algorithm, in terms of *BD-Rate* and *Time-Saving*. As can be noted, the average speed-up is now improved from the range of 12% to 53% obtained for the FPD algorithm without the MDV-SW approach, as was shown in Table IV, to the range of 41% to 67%. This enhancement is at the expense of bit a rate increase, where the *BD-Rate* is practically doubled compared with the FPD algorithm, due to the error introduced by the FMD algorithm. An initial conclusion that can be drawn from this observation is that the penalty of the fast mode decision is not additive to the penalty due to the fast partitioning decision; instead, the error due to the wrong mode decision is amplified when the wrong PU size classification decision is given.

Table V. Performance results of the Fast Mode Decision (FMD) Algorithm

Classification	Sequence	Frames	MDV		MDV-SW	
			T. Saving (%)	BD-Rate (%)	T. Saving (%)	BD-Rate (%)
Class A (2560x1600)	Traffic	150	30.87	0.5	30.43	0.3
	PeopleOnStreet	150	30.34	0.9	29.84	0.4
Class B (1920x1080)	BasketballDrive	500	31.34	0.6	31.14	0.2
	BQTerrace	600	30.47	0.6	30.30	0.3
	Cactus	500	30.33	0.8	30.12	0.4
	Kimono	240	31.69	0.2	31.16	0.1
	ParkScene	240	30.98	0.2	30.53	0.1
Class C (832x480)	BasketballDrill	500	28.71	1.5	28.41	0.6
	BQMall	600	29.69	1.0	29.21	0.5
	PartyScene	500	29.16	1.0	28.64	0.7
	RaceHorses	300	30.34	0.9	29.65	0.3
Class D (416x240)	BasketballPass	500	30.39	1.3	29.11	0.6
	BQSquare	600	28.27	1.4	28.27	1.0
	BlowingBubbles	500	27.96	1.3	27.96	0.8
	RaceHorses	300	29.04	1.4	28.10	0.6
Class E (128x720)	FourPeople	600	30.53	0.8	30.33	0.3
	Johnny	600	30.90	0.8	30.85	0.4
	KristenAndSara	600	30.60	0.9	30.31	0.4
Class A			30.61	0.7	30.14	0.3
Class B			30.96	0.5	30.65	0.2
Class C			29.48	1.1	28.98	0.6
Class D			28.92	1.3	28.36	0.7
Class E			30.68	0.8	30.50	0.4
AVERAGE			30.10	0.9	29.70	0.4

The first node, $N64+MDV-SW$, achieves an average time saving of around 40%, which is quite similar for the classes A, B, C and D, and only class E reaches a speed-up of over 45%. In terms of rate penalty, the results are also quite uniform, around 1%. Regarding the second node, $N64+N32+MDV-SW$, the time saving increases by 15% with respect to the $N64+MDV-SW$ implementation, achieving a notable average complexity reduction of 55.7%. The average *BD-rate* penalty is nearly doubled, 2.3%, compared with the previous node. Finally, the results for the overall node implementation including the MDV-SW approach, $N64+N32+N16+MDV-SW$, show a considerable complexity reduction of 67%. In terms of rate penalty, the sequences of class A obtain the best performance with a 2.5% *BD-rate*, which is nearly half the average rate increase of 4.6%.

Table VII summarizes the results in terms of the $\Delta BDRate$ and $\Delta Time-Saving$ for the three nodes. In terms of complexity reduction, the MDV-SW algorithm obviously provides the highest reduction for the first node, $N64$, of 30%, which is practically the speed-up achieved when MDV-SW is applied alone.

Table VI. Performance results of Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision (FPMD) algorithm compared to HM16.6

Classification	Sequence	Frames	N64+MDV-SW		N64+N32+MDV-SW		N64+N32+N16+MDV-SW	
			T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)	T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)	T. Saving (%)	BD-rate (%)
Class A (2560x1600)	Traffic	150	41.09	0.9	55.98	2.0	69.55	2.0
	PeopleOnStreet	150	41.09	0.9	55.98	1.6	66.88	3.0
Class B (1920x1080)	BasketballDrive	500	42.56	0.9	59.31	3.2	70.55	8.0
	BQTerrace	600	42.86	0.7	56.70	1.4	67.41	6.5
	Cactus	500	42.00	1.0	55.67	2.1	69.66	3.2
	Kimono	240	44.08	1.1	57.92	6.7	72.23	7.6
	ParkScene	240	43.20	0.8	56.82	1.8	70.64	2.0
Class C (832x480)	BasketballDrill	500	39.41	1.0	54.09	1.5	67.11	2.5
	BQMall	600	40.46	1.2	54.65	2.1	66.29	4.7
	PartyScene	500	40.43	1.3	52.47	1.4	63.68	3.7
	RaceHorses	300	39.60	0.7	53.74	1.5	67.15	5.0
Class D (416x240)	BasketballPass	500	37.97	1.2	50.61	1.9	62.35	3.7
	BQSquare	600	39.01	1.6	50.30	1.8	57.62	5.5
	BlowingBubbles	500	38.36	1.3	48.65	1.4	60.02	3.4
Class E (128x720)	RaceHorses	300	39.20	1.1	49.34	1.5	61.69	3.5
	FourPeople	600	42.14	1.1	58.34	1.9	69.74	4.3
	Johnny	600	50.23	1.3	64.72	4.8	72.96	8.8
	KristenAndSara	600	43.73	1.4	63.63	2.8	71.74	4.6
Class A			41.78	1.0	55.98	1.8	68.24	2.5
Class B			42.94	0.9	57.30	3.0	70.14	5.5
Class C			39.97	1.1	53.75	1.6	66.09	4.0
Class D			38.64	1.3	49.74	1.7	60.46	4.0
Class E			45.48	1.3	62.33	3.2	71.51	5.9
AVERAGE			41.67	1.1	55.71	2.3	67.34	4.6

However, for the full node implementation, namely $N64+N32+N16$, the speed-up of the MDV-SW is just around 15%, because the fast mode partitioning has already reduced the complexity by 50%, so the 30% speed-up due to the fast mode decision just affects the remaining 50% of the computational burden. Therefore, the benefits of the fast mode decision are masked when high complexity reduction is achieved by the fast partitioning decision.

The behaviour of the rate penalty is quite different from the time saving. Unexpectedly, for the first two nodes, $N64+MDV-SW$ and $N64+N32+MDV-SW$, the rate increase due to the fast mode decision is practically the same, 1%. The *BD-rate* obtained for the MDV-SW standalone implementation, 0.4%, is practically doubled when it is computed jointly with the fast partitioning mode, for both nodes.

Nevertheless, in the overall implementation, namely $N64+N32+N16+MDV-SW$, the *BD-rate* increase due to MDV-SW is multiplied by 6 compared with MDV-SW alone, an increase of 2.3% with respect to the rate penalty of the same node without the MDV-SW approach.

Table VII. Performance differences between the non-combined proposals and the combined proposals for each node

Classification	Sequence	N64		N64+N32		N64+N32+N16	
		vs.		vs.		vs.	
		N64+MDV-SW		N64+N32+MDV-SW		N64+N32+N16+MDV-SW	
		$\Delta T.Saving$ (%)	$\Delta BDRate$ (%)	$\Delta T.Saving$ (%)	$\Delta BDRate$ (%)	$\Delta T.Saving$ (%)	$\Delta BDRate$ (%)
Class A (2560x1600)	Traffic	29.49	0.90	26.59	1.02	12.94	0.40
	PeopleOnStreet	30.27	0.99	27.95	1.04	16.79	1.88
Class B (1920x1080)	BasketballDrive	28.20	0.72	22.44	0.79	11.35	4.93
	BQTerrace	28.71	0.65	25.75	0.68	14.84	5.22
	Cactus	28.82	0.91	25.89	1.03	12.71	1.07
	Kimono	28.65	0.96	24.02	1.52	10.18	2.31
	ParkScene	28.68	0.78	26.08	0.91	11.89	0.37
Class C (832x480)	BasketballDrill	29.14	1.04	26.46	1.06	13.62	0.15
	BQMall	29.57	1.19	27.77	1.27	15.52	2.26
	PartyScene	30.24	1.33	30.39	1.34	18.19	1.61
	RaceHorses	29.35	0.73	27.34	0.78	14.01	3.31
Class D (416x240)	BasketballPass	31.98	1.19	27.08	1.24	16.69	1.59
	BQSquare	30.19	1.56	29.21	1.57	22.01	4.42
	BlowingBubbles	31.55	1.32	30.07	1.35	19.46	1.67
	RaceHorses	31.07	1.0	29.59	1.11	18.49	1.67
Class E (128x720)	FourPeople	29.66	1.08	24.45	1.13	13.10	2.36
	Johnny	23.42	1.03	19.18	1.39	9.96	4.39
	KristenAndSara	28.36	1.12	19.24	1.15	10.54	1.94
Class A		29.88	0.95	27.26	1.03	14.78	1.14
Class B		28.61	0.81	24.80	0.99	12.12	2.78
Class C		29.58	1.07	27.96	1.11	15.26	1.83
Class D		31.20	1.28	28.97	1.32	19.09	2.34
Class E		27.02	1.08	20.83	1.23	11.14	2.90
AVERAGE		29.25	1.03	25.89	1.13	14.26	2.31

C. Comparison with other Fast Intra-Prediction Algorithms

In Section III, several fast intra-prediction algorithms were described. In this sub-section, a performance comparison between those proposals and the FPMD proposed in this paper is carried out. The simulation results have been reported in Table VIII using the same JCT-VC test sequences, CTCs and performance metrics, in order to show a fair comparison.

The Sun *et al.* algorithm [16] can be considered the best performing algorithm in the balance of time saving, 50%, and bit rate penalty, 2.3%. The Sun *et al.* proposal outperforms the FPMD (*N64+MDV-SW*) implementation in terms of encoder time reduction, with 50% instead of 41.67%, but the bit rate penalty also increases by over 1.2%.

Finally, the reported results prove that the proposed FPMD algorithm for the overall implementation (*N64+N32+N16+MDV-SW*) achieves the highest time saving for intra-prediction coding of over 67% compared with the HEVC reference model, and it outperforms the best proposal in the balance of complexity reduction and bit rate penalty.

Table VIII. Performance comparison between FPMD and the Related Works

	Sun [16]	Huang [17]	Cen [18]	Tian [19]	Khan [20]
Time Saving	50%	20%	16%	29%	42%
BD-Rate	2.3%	0.5%	2.8%	0.5%	1.2%
	Jiang [21]	Chen [22]	Yan [23]	Silva [24]	Yao [25]
Time Saving	20%	37.6%	23.5%	20%	36.2%
BD-Rate	0.74%	1.65%	1.30%	0.9%	1.86%
	Shen [26]	Kim [27]	FPMD (N64+MDV-SW)	FPMD (N64+N32+ MDV-SW)	FPMD (N64+N32+N16+ MDV-SW)
Time Saving	21%	30.5%	41.67%	55.71%	67.3%
BD-Rate	1.7%	1.2%	1.1%	2.3%	4.6%

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented a *Unified Architecture* to form a novel fast HEVC intra-prediction coding algorithm, denoted as *Fast Partitioning and Mode Decision* (FPMD), which combines a *Fast Partitioning Decision* (FPD) algorithm and a *Fast Mode Decision* (FMD) algorithm. The FPD algorithm comprised a three-node decision tree using low complexity attributes, allowing an early CU classification in terms of optimal CTU partitioning, thereby reducing the number of PU sizes to be checked by the RMD and RDO stages. Moreover, the algorithm can be implemented in a scalable way by combining the first node, the first two nodes, or all three nodes, achieving different levels of coding performance. The FMD algorithm is based on the texture orientation detection, by analyzing the MDV along the digital *co-lines*. Instead of 33 angular directions as is defined in HEVC, we have used twelve *co-lines* with rational slopes. The orientation with lower variance is selected as the dominant texture orientation, and a reduced number of directional candidate modes are selected to be further processing by the RDO stage. These approaches can be combined to form the *Unified Architecture* using any combination of nodes, obtaining a wide range of time savings, from 44% to 67%, and light *BD-rate* penalties from 1.1% to 4.6%, with respect to HM 16.6. Comparisons with similar state-of-the-art works show the proposed architecture achieves the best trade-off between complexity reduction and rate-distortion.

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